

**COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PHARMACY LICENSING METHODS
IN THE RUSSIAN FEDERATION AND UZBEKISTAN**

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In the era of globalization, as the boundaries between countries become increasingly indistinct, especially in economic and trade relations, the importance of creating effective and transparent licensing systems becomes a key factor in the successful integration of a state into the global community. Licensing of pharmacies, as an important element in ensuring the quality of medical services and medicines, requires special attention from government agencies and international regulators. In the Russian Federation and Uzbekistan, as countries with transitional economies and active implementation of international standards, licensing processes are undergoing significant changes, reflecting both internal needs to improve the quality of medical services and external requirements for the unification of regulatory procedures.

Comparative analysis of pharmacy licensing in Russia and Uzbekistan is of particular interest to researchers and practitioners in the field of pharmacy and government regulation. This study identifies both unique aspects of each system and common trends that contribute to improving quality and safety standards. In the context of local and global regulatory requirements, an analysis of licensing methods helps

assess the effectiveness of current measures and develop proposals for their optimization and harmonization.

The main goal of this study is to compare pharmacy licensing methods in the Russian Federation and Uzbekistan to identify key differences and similarities, as well as to assess the effectiveness and adaptability of each system to current healthcare requirements and international integration.

Analysis of the regulatory base governing the pharmacy licensing process in Russia and Uzbekistan, including the study of legislative and subordinate acts. Assessment of licensing procedures and requirements to determine their complexity, accessibility, and transparency for pharmacy organizations. Comparison of the roles and powers of regulatory bodies in both countries, studying their impact on the effectiveness and fairness of the licensing process. Identification of the main problems and challenges faced by pharmacies in obtaining a license, based on the analysis of practical cases and expert interviews. Development of proposals for the optimization and harmonization of licensing procedures, based on international best practices and aimed at improving the quality and accessibility of pharmaceutical services.

In Russia, the process of pharmacy licensing is regulated by federal legislation, which sets general requirements for the organization and operation of pharmacy institutions. In recent years, significant changes have been introduced aimed at strengthening the control of the quality of medical goods and services. Scientific works and reports often focus on analyzing these changes, their impact on the availability and quality of pharmaceutical services. Researchers note that despite the strive for improvement, the system faces problems such as the bureaucratization of processes and the inconsistency of legislation implementation at the regional level. In Uzbekistan, reforms in the area of pharmacy licensing are also actively discussed and implemented with the goal of improving regulation and ensuring better access for the population to quality medical drugs. Major scientific publications indicate the country's ambition to create a more transparent and effective licensing system, which includes the introduction of new technological solutions to simplify and accelerate processes.

However, as with Russia, there are problems related to corruption and the need for further strengthening of the legislative base.

Comparative analysis shows that both countries are making significant strides towards improving the pharmacy licensing system, yet they face similar challenges. These studies emphasize the importance of continuous updating of legislation, strengthening institutional mechanisms, and ensuring the enforcement of laws in practice. The influence of international standards and practices is also frequently discussed in the context of their adaptability and application in the conditions of Russia and Uzbekistan. In Russia, pharmacy licensing is regulated by a series of federal laws and subordinate acts, including the Federal Law "On Medicinal Products" and orders from the Ministry of Health. These documents establish the requirements for the operation of pharmacy institutions, the quality, and safety of offered goods. The main regulatory body responsible for oversight and control in the sphere of medicinal products is Roszdravnadzor. This agency handles the issuance of licenses, monitoring their compliance, and taking action in case of violations. In recent years, the focus has been on tightening control and increasing the accountability of pharmacies, necessitated by the need to combat the illegal circulation of medical drugs and increase public trust in the pharmaceutical industry. In Uzbekistan, the licensing process is also strictly regulated by the state. The Law "On Medicinal Products and Pharmaceutical Activities" and corresponding decrees of the Cabinet of Ministers establish the rules for conducting pharmaceutical business, including licensing requirements. The main regulatory body is the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which through its territorial divisions oversees the compliance of pharmacies with legislation. Lately, the government of Uzbekistan has been actively working on strengthening measures aimed at modernizing and simplifying the licensing process using digital technologies, which allows for speeding up the licensing procedure and increasing its transparency.

The basis of the study is a detailed analysis of regulatory legal acts governing pharmacy licensing in both countries. This includes studying federal laws, government decrees, regulatory documents, and guidelines published by official regulatory bodies.

This method allows for identifying formal requirements and procedures, as well as assessing changes in legislation in recent years. To gain a deeper understanding of the practical application of legislation and identify informal aspects of licensing, interviews are conducted with experts in the field. Experts include pharmacists, heads of pharmacy chains, representatives of regulatory bodies, and scientists. Interviews help to identify real problems and challenges faced by market participants, and understand how theoretical provisions are implemented in life.

Comparative analysis involves comparing the data obtained about licensing in Russia and Uzbekistan to identify similarities and differences in approaches to regulating pharmacy activities. Comparative analysis helps to assess the effectiveness of each system and propose possible improvements based on best practices. Studying specific cases of violations of licensing requirements, as well as successful practices in the field of licensing, allows for a more detailed examination of issues related to the application of legislation in real conditions. This method promotes a deep understanding of the issues and the development of specific recommendations for improving regulatory mechanisms.

To conduct an objective comparative analysis of pharmacy licensing methods in the Russian Federation and Uzbekistan, clear comparison criteria must be established. These criteria will allow for assessing various aspects of licensing and its impact on the operation of pharmacy institutions in both countries. In this study, we used criteria such as: Transparency of procedures, assessment of the degree of openness and accessibility of information about the licensing process, including the clarity of requirements and criteria necessary for its acquisition. Bureaucratic burden, analysis of the number of necessary procedures, documents, and time required to complete the licensing process. Includes an assessment of the complexity and time costs to obtain all necessary approvals and agreements. Cost of licensing, assessment of financial costs for obtaining and maintaining a license, including official fees and possible unofficial expenses. Control by state bodies, assessment of the effectiveness and intensity of supervision over the activities of licensed pharmacies, as well as measures taken by

regulators in case of violations. Flexibility and adaptability of the system, analysis of the ability of licensing to adapt to changes in the industry and external environment, including the introduction of new technologies and response to changes in medical and pharmaceutical legislation. Protection of consumer rights, assessment of measures taken within the framework of licensing to ensure the quality and safety of pharmaceutical goods and services offered to end-users. Impact on market competitiveness, studying how licensing affects the ability of new pharmacies to enter the market and compete with already established pharmacy chains. These criteria create a foundation for comprehensive and multi-level analysis of licensing methods, allowing not only to identify key differences between the regulatory systems of Russia and Uzbekistan but also to propose ways of their optimization in the interests of improving the quality of service to the population and maintaining a healthy competitive environment in the pharmaceutical market.

Pharmacy licensing in Russia is regulated at the federal level and requires pharmacy institutions to comply with a strict set of norms and standards. The process of obtaining a license includes the submission of an extensive package of documents, which requires detailed knowledge of the legislation and strict compliance with all prescriptions. Key bodies responsible for the issuance and control of licenses are Roszdravnadzor and its territorial subdivisions. These bodies conduct regular checks to ensure compliance with licensing conditions, including the quality of services provided and the conditions for storing medications. Special attention in regulation is paid to combating the spread of counterfeit products and maintaining high standards of pharmaceutical activity. In recent years, Russian legislation in the field of pharmacy licensing has become stricter. New requirements have been introduced for the minimum area of trading premises, the mandatory presence of pharmaceutical education among owners and employees of pharmacies, and enhanced control over the conditions for storing medical drugs. These measures are aimed at improving the quality of service and ensuring the safety of patients. As part of the federal "Digital Economy" program, pharmacy licensing processes are also undergoing modernization.

The introduction of electronic licenses and the possibility of submitting applications in electronic form reduce administrative barriers and simplify the interaction of pharmacies with regulatory bodies. To combat the illegal circulation of medical drugs, Russia is actively developing a system for monitoring the circulation of drugs, including the introduction of mandatory marking of drugs. This not only allows for tracking the movement of each package of medicine from the manufacturer to the end consumer but also provides an additional level of control within the licensing requirements. Given the importance of professionalism in the pharmaceutical industry, Russian legislation requires regular training and certification of specialists working in pharmacies. This is aimed at improving the quality of service and ensuring compliance with modern standards of medical care.

Pharmacy licensing in Uzbekistan is also subject to strict state regulations, the purpose of which is to ensure the quality and accessibility of medical drugs for the population. The licensing process requires compliance with a number of criteria related to the qualifications of personnel, the technical equipping of pharmacies, and compliance with sanitary norms. The main regulatory body is the Ministry of Health, which through its subdivisions controls the activities of pharmacies locally. Lately, there has been a trend in the country towards simplifying and digitizing the licensing process, which includes the introduction of online services for submitting applications and documents, significantly reducing the time and simplifying the procedure for obtaining licenses. As part of efforts to improve the business climate and stimulate the private sector, the government of Uzbekistan is actively working on simplifying licensing procedures. This includes reducing the number of necessary documents and the timeframes for reviewing applications, making the process more transparent and accessible to entrepreneurs. Uzbekistan is implementing information systems for centralizing and automating licensing processes. For example, the introduction of electronic licenses and the ability to submit applications through specialized web portals significantly simplify and accelerate the process of obtaining necessary permits. In order to strengthen control over the quality of pharmaceutical activity and

compliance with licensing conditions, Uzbek regulatory bodies are increasing the number of pharmacy checks. This includes not only regular inspections but also sudden checks to ensure compliance with standards and storage conditions of medicines. In recent years, Uzbekistan has been paying increased attention to the qualifications of pharmacy personnel. Tightening the requirements for educational level and professional training of pharmacists is aimed at improving the quality of service and increasing consumer trust in pharmaceutical services. Uzbekistan actively interacts with international organizations and neighboring countries to harmonize its regulatory standards with global practices. This helps the country adapt the best practices and standards in the field of licensing and control over pharmaceutical activity.

Comparative analysis of the strengths and weaknesses of pharmacy licensing systems in Russia and Uzbekistan allows identifying key features and potential areas for improvement in each country. The Russian pharmacy licensing system is characterized by a high degree of control over compliance with standards and norms. This includes regular checks of pharmacies for compliance with legislative requirements, which helps maintain a high level of quality of services and goods provided. The introduction of a mandatory system of marking medicinal products significantly increases the transparency of their circulation, helping to combat counterfeit products and providing consumers with verified and safe medical goods. Regulations require that pharmacy employees regularly upgrade their qualifications, which contributes to more quality and professional customer service. Obtaining a license may be associated with the need to provide a large number of documents and go through many stages, which prolongs the process and creates additional complexities for entrepreneurs. Depending on the region, control over compliance with licensing requirements may vary, which leads to inconsistency in the quality of service and the level of availability of pharmaceutical services throughout the country. In conditions of frequent changes in legislation, pharmacies sometimes find it difficult to quickly adapt to new requirements, which can lead to temporary difficulties in their

activities. Legislative requirements for pharmacy premises may be too strict, making it difficult to open new pharmacies, especially in sparsely populated or remote areas.

Uzbekistan has made significant strides in simplifying and accelerating the procedures for obtaining licenses for pharmacies. This includes reducing bureaucracy and switching to electronic forms of document submission, which reduces the time and financial costs for entrepreneurs. The introduction of information technologies, such as electronic licenses and online application submission, makes the process more transparent and accessible. This also facilitates better monitoring and control over the activities of pharmacies. Improving the requirements for education and qualifications of pharmacy personnel is aimed at increasing the quality of service and increasing consumer trust in pharmaceutical services. Despite efforts to modernize, the legislative and regulatory base in Uzbekistan still requires additional strengthening and clarification to meet international standards and best practices. Despite improved processes, the system of control over compliance with licensing conditions may lack resources, which reduces its effectiveness and can lead to violations, remaining without due attention. Similar to Russia, regional differences in the interpretation and application of licensing requirements in Uzbekistan can create an unpredictable environment for business. Although the country is actively working on implementing international standards, integration with the global pharmaceutical practice is still in the process of development, which may hinder access to the latest medical drugs and technologies. In Russia, the strictness of regulation and increased requirements for the quality and safety of medicinal products contribute significantly to increasing consumer trust in the pharmaceutical sector. The system of tracking and marking drugs reduces the risk of counterfeit products and promotes a more transparent and safe market. However, bureaucratic burden and the complexity of obtaining licenses can restrain the entry of new players into the market and limit competition, potentially leading to high prices and a smaller choice for consumers. Regional differences in the application of legislation also create unequal conditions for pharmacies, affecting their ability to function effectively. In Uzbekistan, the simplification and digitization of

licensing procedures have significantly improved the business environment, making the market more open and accessible to new participants. This promotes increased competition, lower prices, and improved customer service. However, deficiencies in the regulatory base and limited resources for control can undermine these achievements, leaving room for dishonest practices and reducing the quality of services provided. Insufficient integration with international standards may also limit access to the latest medical drugs and innovative technologies.

International practice is often characterized by a balance between the need to protect public health and creating a favorable environment for business. Key elements include transparent procedures, minimizing bureaucracy, strict control of quality and safety, and active use of digital technologies to simplify processes. Countries with developed pharmaceutical markets, such as the USA and EU countries, pay special attention to ensuring the availability and quality of medical services, while supporting competition and innovation in the industry. In Russia, strict control and detailed regulation, characteristic of the local licensing system, meet international requirements for protecting quality and safety. However, a high level of bureaucracy and the complexity of procedures can restrain business activity and innovation. In this context, Russia could benefit from simplifying licensing processes and enhancing the use of IT solutions, similar to practices used in the European Union, where great attention is paid to reducing administrative barriers. On the other hand, Uzbekistan is actively working on simplifying and digitizing its procedures, which brings it closer to international standards for ease of doing business. This creates favorable conditions for the development of the private sector and stimulates competition. However, issues of strengthening the legislative base and resources for effective supervision remain relevant, as in countries with developed markets, these aspects are key to maintaining high standards of safety and quality.

Russia demonstrates a high level of strictness in regulating pharmacies, which helps ensure the quality and safety of pharmaceutical products. However, the accompanying bureaucracy can hinder the development of the industry and affect the

timeliness of serving market needs. Uzbekistan, on the other hand, is actively working on simplifying and digitizing processes, which creates favorable conditions for doing business, but faces problems in ensuring sufficient control and supervision. Both Russia and Uzbekistan face the challenge of finding the optimal balance between the need for strict control and providing sufficient flexibility to stimulate growth and innovation in the pharmaceutical sector. Simplifying administrative procedures and implementing digital technologies can help both countries improve the current state of licensing. Comparing with international practices shows that integration with global standards and best practices can significantly enhance the effectiveness of national licensing systems. This includes strengthening the legislative base and developing infrastructure for quality and safety control of pharmaceutical products. Based on these findings, it is important to conduct further research for a deeper analysis of the impact of national regulatory policies on the availability and quality of medical goods and services, as well as their compliance with international standards.

Both countries could benefit from further simplification of the licensing process. This includes minimizing the necessary documents, reducing the timeframes for reviewing applications, and reducing administrative barriers, which can significantly improve the business environment and contribute to the growth of the industry. Expanding the use of digital technologies in licensing processes, such as electronic document management and automation of various stages, will help increase the transparency of processes, reduce the possibility of corrupt actions, and simplify the interaction between pharmacies and regulatory bodies. Aligning national laws with international standards and practices is key to ensuring the quality and safety of medical goods. Developing and implementing uniform standards and criteria for licensing across all regions of the country will improve the consistency and effectiveness of regulatory policy. Improving mechanisms for monitoring compliance with licensing conditions is necessary to maintain high service standards. This may include regular inspections, as well as the implementation of a system for consumer feedback and complaints to respond promptly to possible violations. Continuous

professional development of pharmacy staff should be an ongoing process. Introducing mandatory training and certification programs for pharmacists will help ensure a high professional level and compliance with modern quality requirements. Investments in developing infrastructure and technologies for state supervision will improve monitoring and data analysis capabilities, enhancing the effectiveness of control and allowing for prompt identification and resolution of issues in the licensing system.

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